
Long Term Archives technology trends and evolution

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The ESA EO Space Data Preservation System has the main objective of providing the required infrastructure and services to ensure archiving, preservation and retrieval of ESA Heritage and Earth Explorer Missions, and ESA managed Third Party Missions (TPM) EO data records and associated information. In addition, the ESA EO Space Data Preservation System provides support to the cooperation activities with national and international organisations in the data preservation domain.

The System is composed of several (sub-)systems and services, among them, the EO Space Data Preservation Archive offers long term archival capabilities with state-of-the-art technology.

The main challenge of the archive is the sheer volume of data, the copious number of files and the diversity of formats.

To keep up with the always growing amount and variety of data produced by different missions and sensors, the archive is constantly enhanced to facilitate the archival process by using technological innovation and practices. To save energy, thus making the archive and its hardware environmentally friendly, green computing technologies are favourable.

This paper describes the functionalities and the architecture of the archive located at ESA/ESRIN premises in Frascati (Rome – Italy), the data archived, the different challenges driving its evolution and the planned future upgrades that will ease archiving operations of ESA and TPM Earth Observation Data records.

Keywords: Archive, Tape, Library, Storage, Technology, Evolution, ESA, Earth Observation,

Introduction

The EO Space Data Preservation System (SDPS) is composed of several (sub-)systems and services and has the main objective to ensure ESA Heritage and Earth Explorer Missions, and ESA managed Third Party Missions (TPM) EO Space Data Packages holdings (i.e. Space data and associated technical information) preservation, and to support the cooperation activities across ESA and with national and international organisations in the data preservation domain.

The focus of the SDPS is the Space Data Packages which consist of:

- Space-borne data held or owned, and managed by ESA
- Payload instrument data from ESA and/or Third Party satellites
- Spacecraft telemetry data, auxiliary and ancillary data about satellites and instruments
- Campaign data, calibration and validation data
- Space weather and space debris data
- Higher-level data processed from the above data types
- Browse images and descriptive metadata
- Technical and Scientific Information related to Space-borne Data (from ESA, Industries, and Scientists) necessary or useful for intelligibility, usability and exploitation
- Software and Data Analytics Tools related to Space-borne Data necessary or useful for usability and exploitation

The Space Data Preservation Archive, in cooperation with a second archive outside ESA premises (referred to as the ESA EO Space Data Master Archive), provides the data archiving and preservation function for all ESA managed Earth Observation data (excluding Copernicus Sentinels). The Space Data Preservation Archive also provides a back-up function for space data from other ESA directorates.

Space Data Preservation Archive overview

The Space Data Preservation Archive is a data archive deployed at ESA/ESRIN in Frascati (Rome – Italy) to allow seamless archiving and extraction of data. The archive is the core of the following long term archiving services:

- Back-up of all Master Datasets archived in the ESA EO Space Data Master Archive
- Long Term Archive of ESA EO Datasets not part of the “Master” suite (e.g. Unconsolidated data, flagged data)
- Direct ingestion of ESA and TPM Live Missions
- Disaster Recovery Archive of Master Datasets from other ESA directorates (SCI, HRE, OPS)

The Archive main peculiarities are the following:

- Seamless archiving of ESA and TPM EO Live Missions (24/7)
- Quick bulk data ingestion and extraction (e.g. from or in support of reprocessing campaigns)
- Data can be archived near-line or off-line
- Data is only bulk extracted
- No access to end users
- Power efficient solution to be favoured
- Data to be duplicated
- Archive capable of handling increase of data produced (yearly increase of 5PB per year)

Two copies of all the data are archived at ESRIN premises in two separate buildings using different technology to comply with internationally recognised preservation guidelines [1]. Two Robotic Tape Libraries are the final tier of the multi-tier storage environment. The main Tape Library is capable of storing 36 Petabytes of near-line data in its current form with future system enhancements able to raise storing capabilities and performance. The Main Tape Library is connected via a dedicated 16 Gbps fibre connection to the Disaster Recovery Tape Library.

Data is initially written to fast SSD based storage and is mostly received over 10GB network or from mass storage connected to dedicated incoming stations.

Figure 1 - Archive Infrastructure

Data clients can access the data archived on the main Library over a file-system that can be mounted over Network protocols.

Using Tape storage offers several advantages over disk-based storage:

- The Archive is easy to expand
- Tapes are cheap compared to disk counterparts
- Tape evolution is on par with disk evolution
- Malicious encryption or deletion of data is not achievable. The data seen by data client is virtually presented by a file-system. If these data are compromised, it could be restored from back-ups in within hours

Data ingested and archived

The archive receives 24/7 Payload instrument data from ESA and/or TPM satellites, moreover, the archive receives and supports a vast variety of different type of data and formats including:

- Spacecraft telemetry data
- Spacecraft Payload instrument data in its native format
- Auxiliary data
- Binary files

Figure 2 - Archive Figures (March 2023)

At time of writing of this paper, the archive contains more than 17 Petabytes (PB) of data in native or EO-SIP format. When possible, Earth observation data is converted before ingestion into the EO-SIP submission Information packages format which is the archiving and dissemination packaging format for most ESA Earth Observation missions. EO-SIP represents the package which includes the actual product in its native format, a quality report, a quick-look picture and metadata.

The metadata is an xml file following the OGC standards “Earth Observation profile of Observations & Measurements (OGC EOP O&M)” OGC 10–157. The archive contains data both in native and EO-SIP format for some missions plus data before and after consolidation activities (see Figure 4).

Figure 3 - EO-SIP Adoption

Mission	Uncons.	Cons.	Native	EO-SIP	LIVE
ERS-1/2	X	X	X	X	
Envisat	X	X	X	X	
Cryosat-2	X	X	X	X	X
SMOS	X	X	X		X
SWARM	X		X		X
AEOLUS				X	X
Goce	X	X	X	X	
Oceansat	X		X	X	X
Adeos	X		X		
ALOS	X	X	X	X	X
GOSAT	X		X	X	X
Ikonos-2	X		X	X	
IRS-P3	X	X	X	X	
JERS-1	X	X	X	X	
Kompsat-1	X		X		
Landsat-1,8	X	X	X	X	X
MOS-1,1b	X	X	X		
Nimbus	X		X		
NOAA-7,19	X	X	X	X	
ODIN	X		X		X
PROBA-1	X		X		X
QuickSCAT	X		X		
Rapideye	X		X		
Scisat	X		X		X
Seasat	X	X	X	X	
SeaStar	X		X		
SPOT1-2	X	X	X	X	
TerraSAR	X		X		
WorldView-1,3	X		X	X	
Windsat	X		X		

Figure 4 - Archive Data Holdings

Data flow

ESA and TPM active missions data are pushed from their respective ground segments to a Front-End data circulator which ensures delivery of one copy to the Master Archive, an external archive implemented through a dedicated service awarded to industry, and of a second copy to the Space Data Preservation Archive at ESRIN (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Data Circulation

Once the data has been ingested and validated, confirmation reports are sent to the Mission Payload Data Ground Segment via standard network transfer protocol. Data coming from reprocessing campaigns is received on storage devices or over network protocols.

The archive front-end is a hierarchical storage management (HSM) system with data moved into storage tiers depending on user defined rules. The final tier being always tapes of the two Tape Libraries (Main, Disaster Recovery):

- Online data – Fast RAID storage with Solid State Disks
- Online data – Slow RAID storage with mechanical disks
- Near-line data – Tapes inside the Tape Library
- Off-line data – Tapes outside the Tape Library

When required, tapes are moved outside the Tape Library and extraction of data requires an intervention of an operator. With the data always ending onto tapes, the archive has no actual size limitation and on-line and near-line data limitations depend on tape technology. The tiers are seen by data clients as a single logical archive location that can be accessed using classical network protocols or using a specific proprietary client where metadata is mounted over network, but any Read and Write operations are routed through fibre optic. Clients therefore can list and read the data no matter what tier it is, in the background, the HSM moves the data across the tiers accordingly. When data is first received, it is written onto the fast online data storage, when data is read, it is moved from whatever tier it is, into the fast online storage.

The integrity of the data archived is checked by an ingestion software specifically developed for the matter; the software validates the data and extracts metadata. Metadata is used to populate its Database to be used for advanced queries.

Along with integrity checks, the ingestion software performs other tasks such as:

- Metadata validation (mandatory fields, formatting etc.)
- Checksum calculation of both the EO-SIP package and contained Payload instrument data
- Population of a harvesting directory
- Generation of ingestion reports
- Generation of reports used to populate a Data Information System in charge of managing metadata information for all products generated

When the data has been ingested and validated, it is moved onto its final location in the directory structure on the file system. The directory structure is built using metadata and sorts the data in a standard format:

- Dataset Unique ID/Mission/Product Type/YYYY/MM/DD/EO Product or EO-SIP

Once in its final location, data is written onto tapes of the two tape libraries. The task is automated and monitored by several software and teams. Tapes of the Disaster Recovery Library are unloaded from

the library once full and a procedure to move them offline is executed. Tapes are placed in a secure area on premise. An external site is being identified and shall be used for the task.

The overall archiving of data is monitored by different monitoring systems monitoring different components and workflows. Tape failures are predicted when read or write retries or failures are noticed. Even if still functioning, if a tape has reached its threshold of failed read or write attempts, it is placed into a staging area and its content copied over a new tape. Two drives of the Tape Library are dedicated to tape recovery procedures.

Over the course of its operative life, the archive has been receiving an always increasing number of files and while the initial population has been performed mostly with storage media, incoming data is now mostly received over the Network. To cope with the increasing data received, the Network environment has been updated from Gigabit to 10 GB with future updates already envisaged. The fiber optic connections have been updated from 8 Gbps to 16 Gbps.

The boost of performances allowed the archive to receive up to 13 TB of data daily with peaks of 15 TB received on busy days.

Figure 6 - Data received trend

Challenges of “Preserving long-term data at the Exa-scale”

Over the course of its operative life, many challenges have arisen and a consequent upgrade of the Hardware, Software and Network environment has been constantly performed to enhance and increase overall performances.

Some outstanding challenges require an overall of the environment or data flow:

- Data produced is always increasing
- Performance degradation when dealing with small files. The file-system accessed by data client is partly based on a physical storage with Hard Drives. The filesystem metadata shared the physical storage and the I/O of the daily operations affected performances. Reading, moving, copying and deleting lots of small files required constant updates of the metadata and affected performances
- The Archive Manager ceased being maintained by its vendor. A migration towards an alternative is therefore required and it has proven to be a complicated matter. Alternative Archive Managers are often not compatible with the current metadata meaning all data (17PB) needs to be read from tapes to be migrated to such solution. Moreover, some of these alternatives offer some licensing scheme where you pay for what you read or archive. This is not applicable in the archive due to constant data migration over new tapes

Moreover, a serious of minor challenges affected daily operations:

- Media failures recovery takes time and uses resources. Each time a drive is suspected to have media failures, it has to be read and the data copied over a brand-new tape. For the matter two drives are dedicated to the task impacting activities

- Lots of false media failures alarms. Some external factors may result in media failures false alarms and when that happens it is complicated to troubleshoot and the tapes are simply declared faulty
- Tape Library support requires lots of data collection even for obvious failures. Modern Tape Libraries come equipped with systems designed for data collection. When a library hasn't got such systems, logs and dump collection are to be performed manually even for obvious failures (tape stuck, drive unresponsive etc.)
- Tape Library support often result in requests to update firmware. Even for obvious failures, the support often suggests to update the firmware of the drive and asks to gather logs and dumps once again after the update and after testing. Firmware updates are complicated and time consuming
- Firmware update of a single tape drive means all the other drives needs to be updated to maintain firmware coherence
- Longevity of technology has side-effects (maintenance costs, obsolescence of HW)
- Tape prices are not predictable. T10K tapes prices doubled when its vendor declared the end of life of the tape family. LTO-8 tape shortage in mid-2019 due to patent infringement battle meant LTO-8 tapes were unavailable for a long period of time
- With the end of some tape families and HSM archive managers, it is feared that the main vendors are moving away from tape archive solutions
- Extracting data from tapes is slow and complicated. With the current Archive Manager it is not possible to read data sequentially from a tape

Archive evolution

The archive has been upgraded and, over the course of the last 15 years, several hardware upgrades have been performed to the core of the Tape Library to keep up with the growing amount and variety of data produced.

Outstanding upgrades have been performed to boost performances of the Tier1, the physical storage the data is initially written on. The storage has been separated from the file-system metadata once it had been noticed that lots of I/O affected performances due to the metadata being updated too often. Moreover, the storage was migrated onto Solid State disks.

Tape drives have been updated every ~3/5 years to both boost performances and, to have an opportunity to migrate data from older tapes onto new ones:

- Archive Kick-off – T10000B Drives – 120 MB/s – 1000 GB uncompressed capacity
- 2015 – Migration to T10000D – 250 MB/s – 8500 GB uncompressed capacity
- 2018 – Introduction of LTO-7 – 300 MB/s – 6000 GB uncompressed capacity
- 2021 – Migration to LTO-8 – 360 MB/s – 12000 GB uncompressed capacity

Scripts to read data sequentially have been created internally and drives are always dedicated to the activity of media migration.

Future missions being launched by ESA are already being assessed, the archive has been benchmarked with 8 TB of additional data received daily to confirm it is ready to archive Biomass and EarthCARE, ESA Earth Explorer missions planned to be launched in 2024. Along with fine tuning the archive, the sizing of all the tiers is being increased to allow for any unlikely failures and consequent downtime.

Figure 7 - Archive Upgrades

Additional upgrades are being taken into consideration to handle additional operational scenarios. In the frame of joint “Space Data Preservation Archive” activities, several datasets have been received from external ESA departments. Some of these datasets contained billions of small files. The archive proved to not be ready for the copious number of files and several issues were faced:

- Long time required to copy the data onto the tiers of the archive
- Huge increase of the file-system metadata
- Increased time to backup file-system metadata
- Increased time for file-system simple activities (lists, searches)

Future upgrades shall consider technological innovation and practices we are not familiar with and, to save energy thus making the archive and its hardware environmentally friendly, green computing technologies. An evolution roadmap has been drawn up to address current and future challenges and reach several goals:

- Better ingestion and extraction performances
- Widen the audience using the archive
- Use of innovative technology and archiving trends
- Replacement of Archive Manager middleware that reached its end-of-life
- Ease future migration toward cloud computing (i.e. Object Storage)
- Ingestion of billions of small files
- Decrease the power consumption of the whole environment

Initial assessments have been performed to assess current and future requisites, uses cases and to outline the existing Hardware, Software and workflows involved. A market survey was carried out on archiving and preservation solutions already available on the market. The survey detailed several technologies to be considered:

- Hardware (Tapes, Folio, Glass Drives, Disk Storage, Object Storage Orchestrators etc)
- Software (Alluxio, Atempo, Versity, MinIO, LABDRIVE, nageruHive etc)
- Cloud Providers survey (on prem, public offers etc)
- Standards (OAIS, Core Trust Seam, ISO19086 etc) [2]
- Existing ESA Tools (Copernicus LTA, ESA SCI Planetary Science Archive etc)
- Other Organization (NASA, CERN, NOAA – NCEI, Eumetsat etc)
- Sustainability (Energy consumption, Cooling Requirements etc)
- Costs (HW and SW)

Moreover, it has been highlighted how several organisations are moving to cloud-based services because of their flexibility and cost effectiveness in the short-term. However, the step to cloud needs to be planned because long-term costs and vendor locking could be an issue in the future. Moreover, cloud providers are charging for requests or operations which makes it almost impossible to make a budget in advance.

Complementary to pure cloud solutions, the hybrid-cloud approach is provided by many hardware and software providers. For organisations with already existing infrastructure, it is interesting to see how a mix between public access on the cloud plus cold on-premise storage would benefit in the long-term to address pure cloud flaws.

Security and sustainability are also worries in this market. Several additional key findings were highlighted during the activity which led to the choice to implement a solution for the evolution of the ESA/ESRIN Space Data Preservation Archive still, partially, based on tape libraries.

A final roadmap to perform the actual upgrade of the archive followed:

- Review the existing Hardware on premise
- If needed, new management infrastructure should be acquired to replace current HSM
- If the evolution foresees the Cloud implementation: check if some hybrid-cloud approach could be feasible
- Define which standards need to be followed
- Prepare requirements for the systems to follow and checklists for providers analysis
- Evaluate archiving software alternatives between those existing on the market or build a proprietary solution
- Calculate accurately the current energy consumption and heating dissipation needs for the current solution
- Open RFIs with selected providers to get a deeper technical information (and pricing)

Conclusions

After analysing the market, the current situation of the ESRIN Archive and the future requirements, the best solution for updating the Archive has been identified in a hybrid cloud model, which integrates the current tape storage infrastructure with a flexible model that facilitates access and improves its online capabilities.

The current Tape Library work-life has been considered sufficient to cover the needs of the coming years and therefore, the recommendation is to continue using it for some more years. The archive manager shall be replaced by one of the identified alternatives or by an integration into cloud services. One understated advantage of continuing to use tape-based archives is the always increasing security concerns. Malicious encryption or deletion of the data is not possible or highly complicated in that case. Moreover, using tape storage instead of hard disk is an effective solution to reduce energy consumption and carbon emissions.

The archive evolution is the first step in the direction of assuring seamless archival, extraction, valorisation, and preservation of the always increasing ESA and TPM EO data records and associated information.

References

- [1] CEOS WGISS Best Practices and Guidelines - <https://ceos.org/ourwork/workinggroups/wgiss/preservation/>
[2] CCSDS OAIS - <https://public.ccsds.org/pubs/650x0m2.pdf>